

Studies on Hydroxo Cyanogen Compounds :

IV. Amperometric and Conductometric Studies on the Composition of Cr (III), Mn (II) and Fe (III) Hydroxo Cyanomolybdates

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The composition of freshly precipitated chromium, manganese and iron hydroxocyanomolybdates was determined using amperometric and conductometric techniques. The composition of chromium and iron compounds has been found to be $M^{II} [Mo^{IV} (CN)_4 (OH)_3 (H_2O)]$ whereas the composition of manganese hydroxocyanomolybdate may be given as $KMn^{II} [Mo^{IV} (CN)_4 (OH)_3 (H_2O)]$.

The chemical literature abounds in references on the properties and composition of alkali cyano-ferrates (II & III) and -molybdates (IV & V),^{1,2} but the problem of metal complexes of alkali hydroxocyanomolybdates have attracted little attention by the workers in this field. Only a few workers carried out studies on the metal complexes by the method of chemical analysis^{3,4}. As the physicochemical methods have got certain advantages over the method of chemical analysis, it was thought worthwhile to employ these techniques for the elucidation of metal complexes of hydroxocyanomolybdates.

The present communication deals with our studies on the composition of insoluble Cr (III), Mn (II) and Fe(III) complexes of tripotassium aquo trihydroxotetracyano-molybdate (IV) employing amperometric and conductometric methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tripotassium aquo trihydroxotetracyanomolybdate (IV) dihydrate, $K_3 [Mo (CN)_4 (OH)_3 (H_2O)] \cdot 2H_2O$ ^{1,5}, was prepared by the water hydrolysis of $K_4 [Mo (CN)_4 (OH)_4]$ obtained by the method of Jakob, et al.⁴

All chemicals, molybdenum (VI) oxide, hydrochloric acid, hydrazine sulphate, ammonia, potassium hydroxide, potassium cyanide, used were of A. R. grade. The

1. W. R. Bucknall and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2981.
2. W. U. Malik, et al.; *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 293; *ibid.*, 1962, 39, 356, 844; *Bull. Chem., Soc.*, Japan, 1961, 34, 1306; *Talanta*, 1961, 8, 737; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 20, 155.
3. W. F. Jakob and C. Michalewicz, *Chem. Abst.*, 1933, 27, 5668.
4. Z. Jakob and W. Jakob, *Chem. Abst.*, 1958, 52, 17981.
5. A. W. Adamson and J. R. Perumareddi, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 247.

product of hydrolysis was obtained in the solid state by fractional precipitation with ethanol. The compound (blue in colour) was dried over CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator and analysed. (Calcd. for $\text{K}_3[\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Mo, 22.69; K, 27.77; C, 11.37; N, 13.26; H, 2.15; O, 22.72; Found: Mo, 24.1; K, 28.1; C, 11.99; N, 13.03; H, 2.06; O (by difference, 20, 72%). Its solution was kept stored in dark bottles wrapped with black paper and its concentration was determined by titrating potentiometrically against standard pot. hexacyanoferrate (III) solution⁶.

Chromic chloride (A. R.), ferric ammonium sulphate (A. R.) and manganous sulphate (E. Merck) were used for the preparation of solutions and they were standardized by the usual analytical methods. Fresh solutions were prepared to avoid the error due to hydrolysis.

Polarographic measurements were carried with a Fischer Electropode against a S.C.E. KCl (0.1M) was used as the supporting electrolyte and gelatin (0.01% for Cr^{3+} & Mn^{2+} and 0.02% for Fe^{3+}) as the maximum suppressor. In order to determine the constant potential to be applied during the course of reactions, polarograms for the reduction of various metal ions were taken for the following mixtures:

- (i) 0.4 ml CrCl_3 (0.1M) + 2ml KCl (1.0M) + 2ml gelatin (0.1%) + 15.6 ml water.
- (ii) 0.5 ml MnSO_4 (0.1M) + do + do + 15.5 ml water.
- (iii) 0.8 ml $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (0.1M) + do + 4 ml gelatin (0.1%) + 13.2 ml water.

The polarograms were drawn (fig. 1) and from the plateau, the potential to be

Fig. 1. Polarograms of (i) CrCl_3 , (ii) MnSO_4 , (iii) $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ and (iv) $\text{K}_3[\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$.

applied during amperometric titrations were found out. The potential applied during the course of titrations for Cr (III), and Fe (III), being - 1.3 and -0.45v, respectively.

The amperometric titrations between Mn (II) and hydroxocyanomolybdate were not carried out according to the reduction wave of $MnSO_4$ as hydrogen wave interferes with the reduction. As the hydroxocyanomolybdate is itself oxidisable at the d.m.e. giving two waves ($E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -0.05v$; $E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -0.3v$.) (Fig. 1, curve (IV)), it is evident that the titrations with Mn (II) may be carried out at an applied potential of 0.0v.

Purified nitrogen gas was used for deaeration.

Conductometric studies were made with the help of Cambridge conductivity bridge (No. L - 350140) with a dip type conductivity cell (No. PR 9510 and cell constant 1.46).

The studies with Cr^{3+} and Fe^{3+} were carried out at 30° and with Mn^{2+} at 70° due to its slow reaction at 30° . The temperature was maintained in a thermostatic water bath within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ accuracy. Both direct (salt solution as the titrant) and reverse (hydroxocyanomolybdate as the titrant) titrations were carried out with Cr^{3+} and Mn^{2+} but with Fe^{3+} only reverse titrations were made.

Typical curves are shown in figs. 2 to 5.

Fig. 2. Amperometric Titration Curves (Direct).
 (i) 20 ml., 0.003M $CrCl_3$ and (II) 10 ml. ; 0.008 M $MnSO_4$ vs. 0.1 M $K_3[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)]$.

Fig. 3. Amperometric Titration Curves (Reverse).
 (i) 20 ml., 0.003 M, (ii) 10 ml., 0.008 M, and
 (iii) 10 ml., 0.004 M $K_3[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)]$ vs.
 0.1 M (i) $CrCl_3$, (ii) $MnSO_4$ and (iii) Ferric alum.

Fig. 4. Conductometric Titration Curves.
 (Direct). 15 ml, 0.005 M (i) $CrCl_3$ and
 (ii) $MnSO_4$ vs. (i) 0.05 M and (ii) 0.10
 M $K_3[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)]$.

Fig. 5. Conductometric Titration Curves (Reverse).
 15 ml., 0.005 M $K_3[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)]$ vs.
 (i) 0.05 M $CrCl_3$, (ii) 0.125 M $MnSO_4$ and
 (iii) 0.2 M Ferric alum.

DISCUSSION

Chromic Hydroxocyanomolybdate Complex: The reaction between chromic chloride and hydroxocyanomolybdate may be given by the stoichiometric equation :
 $CrCl_3 + K_3[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)] = Cr[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)] + 3KCl$.

Both amperometric and conductometric results give a combining ratio of 1 : 1 pointing towards the formation of the complex $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ in accordance to the equation given above.

In direct amperometric titrations the current increases in the beginning and then decreases. This behaviour may be explained on the basis of the solubility of the complex formed whose concentration is very low in the beginning. When the solution becomes saturated with the complex, precipitation occurs and the current begins to decrease. This decrease in current continues till 1 : 1 ratio is reached and then remains constant due to the non-reducibility of the hydroxocyanomolybdate at d.m.e.

Reverse amperometric titration curves are typical in nature but the break near the end point is not very sharp. The difficulty was overcome by extrapolation. The slow increase in current before the end point may be explained by taking into consideration the solubility and hydrolysis of the complex.

Manganese (II) Hydroxocyanomolybdate Complex : The titrations performed between manganese sulphate and potassium aquo hydroxocyanomolybdate solutions provide ample proof regarding the composition of the precipitates obtained by their interaction at 70° . The ratio 1 : 1 for the reactants found on the basis of these titrations points towards the composition $\text{KMn}^{\text{II}}[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ for the complex.

Ferric Hydroxocyanomolybdate Complex : In this case only reverse titrations were performed because dilute solutions of ferric alum hydrolyse readily. The results give a 1 : 1 ratio, therefore the composition of the complex may be given as $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$.

For almost all the different concentrations employed for titrations, the amount of iron required is larger than the theoretical values. This behaviour may be attributed to the adsorptive property of the freshly precipitated complex.

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